

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Rahal****FIRST NAME: Musaab****PROGRAM CODE: DIFE****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Pr. Cleenewerck**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

DO YOU WRITE ESSAY OR ARTICLE?

1)INTRODUCTION

As a required subject of my Ph.D. program at Euclid University, the first period of the first course offers a review of the principles of academic writing. In my opinion, this makes sense. That because academic writing is not as artistic writing or even professional writing. Which the academic writing subject to templates and concepts should be applied by the writers. In contrast to that, the artistic writers or professional writers have more flexibility in using their style of writing. However, the outcomes of the first period of the course ACA-40D (EUCLID 2015, 2), that the students should get skills of how using the techniques associated with writing academic papers. Example, the first skill the students should gain is the writing essay and how to write a good essay. But the subject does not mention the differences and comparisons between the essay and article. That many students and new writers do not distinguish between them. Because of that, I would like to talk about the main differences – article against essay.

2)OVERVIEW OF ACA-401 COURSEPACK

In the beginning, the subject offers the necessary steps of essay writing, such as, at first define the question. Then read about your topic and find credible sources to support your evidence. Organize your project, write your first draft to include your introduction, body, and conclusion. Let your friends read it and finally review it again and do not forget to check the grammar and using the right punctuations (EUCLID 2015, 5).

The next section talks about the template and style of Euclid University that the students should apply them during their writing. Starting with how to save the students'

files with proper format, ending in how to use the punctuation correctly. Prohibitive of plagiarism in general writing and in especially in academic writing, it is essential in Euclid University's regulations (EUCLID 2015, 8). Also, the course talks about how to use the citation, either footnotes or endnotes, that EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian).

Add on that; the course provides a guide of the writing style that needs to be consistent. Style can encompass many different aspects like sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, the use of symbols, structure, and use of headings.

In fact, the course is full of information about the rules of English writing and the difference between American and British English. All points related to English writing were covered. Therefore, for me, especially that I am a foreigner, this benefits me a lot, and I have a greater conviction of the importance of adhering to the rules of writing and respect the reader in terms of providing good writing, useful and free of mistakes as much as possible.

3) DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ARTICLE AND ESSAY

At first, let us define an essay. According to Pediaa (2015) defines essay as “a piece of writing that describes, analyzes and evaluates a certain topic or an issue” (Pediaa 2015, 1). While according to EUCLID (2015) defines essay as “An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2015, 2). Explains more that an academic essay also should answer questions or argument, develop a thesis. Besides, an academic essay should include relevant examples to support the writer's idea, include evidence, and use credible sources.

In contrast, the article can be defined according to Collins (2019) as, a piece of writing that is published in a newspaper or magazine (Collins 2019, 2). Articles can be found in magazines, encyclopedias, websites, newspapers, or other publications. The main aim of an article is to inform the readers about a specific topic. There are many types of articles according to the type of information they present. This information and facts are generally presented since the writer does not aim to persuade the readers to accept his idea or argument but to describe the topic only.

Therefore, it can be summarized the main differences as follow. In terms of purpose, the article is written to inform the readers about some concept. While the essay is generally written as a response to a question or proposition. As a citation, the articles do not require citations or references, whereas the essays require references and citations. Regarding the tone, the articles are more literary as they mostly describe a topic, but the essays are more scientific as they analyses and criticize a topic.

4) GENERAL OF ADVICE FOR A GOOD ESSAY

Through my studies and my review of a subject essay writing (EUCLID 2015, 43). May I summarize the most important suggestions in terms of how to write an academically acceptable essay.

- Stay focused. You need to focus on one question. Without providing a comprehensive overview of your idea. Instead, guide your essay by the particular problems as we said before

- Do not title your essay as generalities. For example, why the water important for humans' lives

- Write clearly. By writing short sentences, avoiding long paragraphs, do not use obscure words such as *non-randomness*

- Do not make your writing clumsy and boring. For example, avoid long sentences that distract the reader. And try not to repeat the same words. Stay away from excessive stuffing and avoid the language of numbers

- Support your essay in evidence and references

- Seriously discuss your argument or ideas. In return, you must respect the views of others and discuss them objectively

- Read your essay out loud when you finish writing

- Finally, do not plagiarize

5) CONCLUSION

In the writing world, writers use various styles and techniques to express their idea. The writing fields are a lot, such as novels, poetry, stories, essays, reports, news articles, et cetera. Some of these writing types are free of any restrictions such as art writing, while some writing types are under standard rules, format, and specific tones such as essays, theses, and dissertations. In other words, academic writing more restricted than professional writing.

As this essay reviewed the differences between the essay and the article. Which writing article more flexible and relatively free to use a specific style or method that the writer preferred. While writing an essay is slightly different, which more restricted and required using of common rules.

In my opinion, writing an article is more interesting to people, because it aims to inform people without persuading them to change their convictions. Such as newspapers and blogging. On the other hand, the essays aim to address the specific issue targeting the educated people and specialized in a field of science.

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